

Adverse soils tolerance

Sensitivity of rice seedlings to salinity

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We experimented to determine the age at which rice seedlings are most sensitive to salinity, using salt-tolerant varieties Nona Bokra and Pokkali and salt-sensitive IR28 and IR2035-117-3.

Pregerminated seeds were sown on Styrofoam sheets, each with 60 holes and a nylon net bottom, at one seed/hole, 60 seeds/variety. The sheets were floated in 40- × 20- × 15-cm plastic trays filled with 9 liters nutrient solution N maintained at pH 5.0. Seedlings were grown at 29/21 °C (day/night) with about 70% relative humidity in the phytotron glasshouse under natural daylight.

Salinity stress of 6,800 ppm (EC 12 dS/m) was introduced by adding 1:1 mixture of NaCl and CaCl₂ to the nutrient solution at 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, and 12 d after seeding. Unsalinized trays of each variety were the checks. Seedling survival was measured 14 d after salinization.

Survival of unsalinized checks of all

varieties was 100%. Salt-tolerant Nona Bokra and Pokkali were not affected by salinity (see table). Seedlings of sensitive variety IR28 were severely affected up to 7 d, then gradually gained tolerance. IR2035-117-3 seedlings showed sensitivity up to 6 d. Varietal differences in salt sensitivity were apparent. Tolerance in sensitive varieties increased with age, showing that seedling age is a critical factor in screening for salt tolerance. □

Rice seedling survival after 14 d salinization (EC = 12 dS/m) pressure applied at different seedling ages. IRRI, 1988.

Variety	Survival (%) at each seedling age (d)									
	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
Nona Bokra	100	100	100	98	96	100	100	100	100	100
Pokkali	82	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
IR28	2	17	12	20	70	70	97	100	100	100
IR2035-117-3	10	52	57	85	93	92	98	100	100	100

Performance of some acid tolerant rice varieties in two acid saline soils of Sunderbans

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Grain yield of promising acid tolerant rice varieties. Sunderbans, India, 1987.

Variety, line	Grain yield (g/plant)	
	Nirdeshkhali	Belakhali
IR28222-9-2-2-2-2	8.9	14.0
RD15	8.1	20.8
S4	6.9	8.3
Gablak - Cablal	6.9	7.4
IET230	6.9	8.6
S3	6.7	8.6
IR8067-41-IE-P1	6.7	12.2
BW100	6.7	10.8
Quisidugo	6.0	5.8
B2443B-KN-10-1-1-1	5.9	11.4
B221496-pn-26-1-1	5.5	12.3
SR26B	5.5	14.8
S5	5.5	13.5
S1	5.5	12.6
Jaca	5.5	10.1
ITA-116	5.5	5.0

We transplanted 51 promising acid tolerant rice varieties and lines collected from Indonesia, West Africa, Thailand, Sri Lanka, Malaysia, Philippines, India, and IRRI in acid saline soils of Nirdeshkhali (ECe 9.3-5.4 dS/m and pH 3.3-3.8) and Belakhali (ECe 4.0-3.0

dS/m, pH 5.0-5.8).

In the highly acid saline soils of Nirdeshkhali, the highest grain yields were from IR28222-9-2-2-2-2, and RD15 (see table). In less acidic conditions, RD15 gave the highest yield, followed by SR26B and IR28222-9-2-2-2-2. □

Integrated germplasm improvement

ADT39, a new rice variety for Tamil Nadu

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ADT39 is a derivative of IR8/IR20 made in 1976. It is a nonlodging semidwarf with 120- to 125-d duration and medium slender white rice.

Good grain yields were recorded in research station, All India Coordinated

Yield of ADT39 in Tamil Nadu, India.

Test	Grain yield (t/ha)		Increase (%)
	ADT39	IR20	
TRRI, Aduthurai	4.8	4.1	17
AICRIP trials (wet season)	3.8	3.3 ^a	15
AICRIP trials (dry season)	5.1	4.5 ^a	13
Adaptive research trials (Thanjavur district)	5.6	4.9	14
Crop cutting experiments (Thanjavur district)	6.3	4.5	40

^aJaya.

Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP), and adaptive trials and in crop cutting experiments in farmers' fields.

Yield increase was 14-40% compared with IR20 and 13-15% compared with Jaya (see table). In AICRIP trials, it was superior to Jaya at six locations during the wet season and two locations during the dry season.

ADT39 is resistant to bacterial blight, blast, neck blast, brown spot, sheath blight, and grain discoloration;

moderately resistant to green leafhopper; and susceptible to sheath rot, leafhopper, and brown planthopper. (However, BPH is not a problem in the season in which it is grown.)

ADT39 has 65% milling recovery and 10.1% protein. The fine-grained rice cooks well and is highly preferred in South India. Farmers of Tamil Nadu have named it "Idly rice" and "tiffin rice." The Agricultural Department

estimated its natural spread, before release, in 40,000 ha in Thanjavur district.

ADT39 is already proven well suited to late planting (Oct-Nov) in Thanjavur district. Because it matures earlier than IR20, it should escape water scarcity during ripening, opening room for timely sowing of black gram, green gram, and cotton in the rice fallow season. □

VL Dhan 163 - a new upland rice variety for Uttar Pradesh hills

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VL Dhan 163, a derivative of IR5904, was released in 1987 for upland Jun sowing in the U.P. hills.

VL Dhan 163 possesses such desirable characteristics as semitall stature, medium grain, and compact panicle with good spikelet fertility. It has moderate tillering ability and matures in 108-113 d. It is tolerant of drought and

low temperature and shows good response up to 60 kg N/ha. It also has shown high resistance to leaf and neck blast, stem borer, and leafhopper (see table).

In 12 trials at different sites in the U.P. hills, VL Dhan 163 produced an average 2.6 t/ha, 41.35% higher than the

national check Bala.

Traditionally, the hill farmers of U.P. grow Mar- or Apr-sown spring rice under rainfed upland conditions in a 2-yr cropping system of spring rice - wheat - finger millet - fallow. With VL Dhan 163, hill farmers will be able to plant two rice crops in a year. □

Plant characteristics of VL Dhan 163 and Bala. Almora, U. P., India, 1987.

Character	VL Dhan 163	Bala (check)
Plant height (cm)	95-100	65-70
Days to 50% flowering	75-80	80-85
Days to maturity	108-113	105-110
1000-grain weight (g)	19.0	16.0
Hulling percentage	85.4	83.7
Grain length (mm)	5.4	4.6
Grain width (mm)	2.2	2.4
Length/width ratio	2.4	1.9
Protein content	9.3	9.0
Yield (t/ha)	2.6	1.8
<i>Disease & insect pest reaction^a</i>		
Leaf blast (0-9 scale)	3	9
Neck blast (0-9 scale)	1	9
Sheath rot (0-9 scale)	3	7
False smut (0-9 scale)	1	5
Stem borer (0-9 scale)	3	5
Leafhopper (0-9 scale)	1	5

^aBy Standard evaluation system for rice. Maximum score recorded during any year 1983-86.

Performance of semidwarf mutants of Basmati 370

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Four semidwarf mutants (gamma

radiation 25 kR) were selected from the segregating population and yield tested in the field. The short-statured mutants gave significantly higher grain yields than parent variety Basmati 370 and had high tillering ability (Table 1) and lodging resistance. Growth duration was similar to Basmati 370. The semidwarf

Table 1. Performance of the induced mutant lines and Basmati 370. Punjab, Pakistan.

Mutant, variety	Plant ht (cm)	Duration (d)	Productive tillers (ns./plant)	Yield (g/plant)	Yield (t/ha)
DM24	122.7	105	15	25	4.6
DM25	125.7	106	15	24	4.6
DM28	131.3	105	12	22	4.2
DM38	121.7	105	14	23	4.1
Basmati 370	160.5	104	12	21	4.0
LSD (0.05)	4.2	ns	2	1	0.1

Table 2. Physicochemical characteristics of rice mutants and Basmati 370. Punjab, Pakistan.

Variety, mutant	Length ^a (mm)	Width ^a (mm)	Length-to-width ratio ^a	Quality index ^a	Elongation ratio ^a	Amylose ^b (%)
DM24	6.9	1.8	3.9	2.3	1.9	24
DM25	6.7	1.7	3.9	2.4	1.9	23
DM28	6.6	1.7	3.8	2.5	1.7	23
DM38	6.7	1.7	3.8	2.4	1.8	23
Basmati 370	6.9	1.8	3.8	2.3	1.8	23
LSD (0.05)	0.15	ns	ns	0.10	ns	ns

^aAv of 10 determinations. ^bAv of 3 determinations.